

RES4CITY CASE STUDY #8

Urban smart manufacturing with carbon sequestration

By University of Coimbra

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Executive Summary

Figure 37. Smart manufacturing in urban areas with carbon sequestration systems - Graphical Abstract

This case study underscores the promise of partnerships between universities and industries to propel the shift towards cleaner energy, reduced carbon emissions, and intelligent manufacturing (Figure 37).

These collaborative efforts extend beyond just financial feasibility, bringing a range of advantages such as enhanced energy reliability, competitiveness, and diminished emissions.

Abstract

Renewable energy communities (REC) and smart manufacturing are gaining attention for their interconnected ability and potential to contribute to a more sustainable future by lowering the environmental impact of production and consumption while boosting efficiency and reducing costs. Their implementation can be mutually beneficial as surplus energy produced by the REC can be harnessed and used by smart manufacturing facilities, thereby

reducing their reliance on traditional fossil fuels, and cutting down carbon emissions. Additional benefits include reduced energy expenses, improved reliability, and decreased vulnerability to energy price fluctuations. In summary, the connection between the two strategies can help improving overall efficiency and sustainability, two fundamental premises of the energy transition process underway.

This case study examines the development of a REC initiative at the University of Coimbra, the oldest higher education institution in Portugal. The analysis includes a characterization of the project and the assessment of its energy, economic and environmental benefits. Furthermore, an empirical evaluation of load diagrams and renewable energy production is performed to illustrate the energy exchange potential of this REC. In the second stage, the study examines how the technologies and tools applied in this case study can be used in a broader interconnected context of smart manufacturing. To this end, it explores the potential impacts and benefits of extending the REC concept to industrial facilities, to promote smart manufacturing through increased performance and sustainability. Carbon emissions and energy costs are focal subjects of this examination. The study concludes with a qualitative theoretical analysis of the implementation of carbon sequestration systems,

evaluating their feasibility, potential benefits, and drawbacks.

The results reveal that the REC has the potential to cover approximately 38.8% of the University's annual electricity consumption, leading to significant reductions in both energy costs and CO₂ emissions and, thereby, advancing the institution's financial and environmental sustainability goals, while progressing towards its carbon neutrality target. Furthermore, these results highlight the project's broader impact, stretching beyond the University's boundaries. Around 40% of the REC's generated energy can be exploited by nearby industrial consumers, enabling them to reduce energy expenses and CO₂ emissions and enhance energy resilience. It also allows them to foster their financial efficiency and environmental responsibility, while promoting smart manufacturing and decarbonization of industries.

This study highlights the potential of collaboration between higher education institutions and industries in advancing energy transition, decarbonization and smart manufacturing. Beyond financial viability, these joint initiatives offer multifaceted benefits, including energy resilience, competitiveness, and reduced emissions. These outcomes underscore the importance of promoting and replicating this model across similar institutions and companies, thereby accelerating the transition towards a sustainable and low-carbon future.

Introduction

The sustainable development of modern societies entails addressing several critical concerns, such as minimizing greenhouse gas emissions and reducing the environmental, social, and economic costs associated with energy production (Giordano et al., 2019). As part of the European Green Deal

(European Commission, 2020), the European Union (EU) set the goal of achieving climate neutrality by 2050, aligning with its commitment to global climate action under the Paris Agreement (European Commission, 2016). Considering that 75% of the EU's greenhouse gas emissions are from energy production and use, the energy transition from fossil fuels to renewable energy sources (RES) is a vital step to decarbonize the EU's energy systems (European Commission, 2022a). In order to increase the penetration of RES in the energy matrix, the Clean Energy for All Europeans package emphasizes the significance of local and decentralized electricity production to accelerate the energy transition by actively engaging citizens in the process through self-consumption or renewable energy communities (REC) (European Commission, 2019).

RECs are legal entities that can be composed of citizens, public institutions, cooperatives, municipalities, small and

medium enterprises and other organizations established with different business models. Currently, the most predominant business models involve generation and supply, collective investments in installations of energy production, and collective self-consumption (European Commission, 2022b). These models can be combined and include variations such as community-owned grids and district heating systems. RECs empower their participants to produce, manage, and consume their own energy, providing access to clean and cost-effective energy solutions. This not only contributes significantly to the economy's growth but also helps reduce carbon emissions and fosters public acceptance of renewable technologies (Kubli & Puranik, 2023).

Achieving these benefits is possible by adjusting or reducing energy demand, especially during periods of high energy prices, and by generating income for the

community through energy trade, taxes, or the creation of new job opportunities (Brummer, 2018). Furthermore, REC effectively addresses the mismatch between energy demand and supply, raises awareness about energy consumption issues, and promotes energy-saving behaviour. They also play a crucial role in reaching renewable energy generation targets (Brummer, 2018; Dai et al., 2015; Koch & Girard, 2011). Although REC offers numerous benefits to society, its implementation faces several barriers. Some of these challenges include complex and burdensome bureaucratic procedures for registration, permitting, grid access, and licensing. Additionally, the high costs of implementation, lack of institutional and political support, general scepticism towards renewable energy, and insufficient financial resources and expertise are obstacles that hinder the widespread adoption of REC (Brummer, 2018).

The implementation of REC in historic buildings, such as the

University of Coimbra, presents specific challenges that need to be considered. These buildings hold a crucial place in the architectural heritage of European countries, constituting nearly 40% of the building stock (Cabeza et al., 2018). However, restoring and retrofitting these structures present intricate challenges due to their unique cultural significance and characteristics (Cabeza et al., 2018). Some of these challenges include potential alterations to the building's identity and historical value, the need to obtain permits and approvals for interventions, and technical limitations associated with older architecture and limited space for RES installations (Marrone et al., 2023).

Considering these limitations, integrating heritage buildings with REC can be highly beneficial. This combination can offer environmental sustainability by reducing the carbon footprint of historic buildings. Additionally, it has

the potential to create opportunities for educational and community engagement, involving students, researchers, faculty, and nearby residents in the design, development, and exploitation processes of such integration. Therefore, historic buildings can embrace modern energy solutions while preserving their cultural significance and fostering a sense of shared responsibility for sustainable development.

While REC contribute significantly to decreasing carbon emissions, it is crucial to find complementary measures for carbon capture, such as nature-based solutions, to help further reduce carbon emissions from the University's operations. As reported by the IPCC, lowering atmospheric CO₂ levels is imperative to limit the global average temperature increase to well below 2°C above pre-industrial levels (Wennersten et al., 2015). To achieve this objective, carbon dioxide removal (CDR) techniques need to complement the

decarbonization of energy-related activities, accomplished by lowering fossil fuel consumption and increasing the penetration of renewable sources (Creutzig et al., 2019; Erbach & Victoria, 2021).

CDR solutions encompass a diverse array of approaches, varying from nature-based methods, which are considered more feasible and cost-effective in the short term, to technological alternatives that may gain relevance in the latter part of the current century (Erbach & Victoria, 2021). Some examples of technological alternatives include Ocean Alkalinization, Enhanced Weathering, Bioenergy with Carbon Capture and Storage (BECCS), and Direct Air with Carbon Capture and Storage (DACCS) (Erbach & Victoria, 2021; University, 2020). Conversely, nature-based methods comprise Forestation, Soil Carbon Sequestration, Biochar, Wetland Restoration, and

Agroforestry (Erbach & Victoria, 2021; University, 2020).

The nature-based solution Agroforestry is a highly cost-effective alternative for carbon capture, holding an estimated annual carbon removal potential of 0.1 – 5.7 GtCO₂ by 2050, while providing significant returns on investment through the trade of its crops (Erbach & Victoria, 2021). Like soil carbon sequestration, agroforestry can even yield negative costs per ton of CO₂ removed, given the economic advantages resulting from enhanced crop productivity (Kim et al., 2016; Zomer et al., 2016). The expenses associated with establishing and maintaining agroforestry systems can vary depending on factors such as site preparation, tree species selection, and management practices. However, once established, agroforestry systems tend to be relatively self-sustaining, requiring minimal inputs and management in comparison to other carbon removal technologies. Furthermore, agroforestry provides additional income

streams by diversifying agricultural production. This highlights the potential of adopting sustainable and profitable practices that contribute not only to climate change mitigation but also to overall economic prosperity.

With the foregoing in mind, the primary objective of this case study is to evaluate the energy, economic and environmental benefits stemming from the development of a REC at the University of Coimbra. Additionally, this study will identify the potential as well as the barriers that can hinder the progress of this project. Subsequently, we will explore how the technologies and tools applied in this case study can be extrapolated and used in a broader interconnected context of smart manufacturing. Finally, we will simulate the implementation of a carbon sequestration nature-based system to assess its feasibility, potential benefits, and drawbacks.

This case study is structured as follows: the subsequent section provides a comprehensive description of the University of Coimbra's case study. Following that, the proposed solution for this case study is delineated. Afterward, some representative results are showcased and subjected to discussion. Finally, conclusions are drawn, and recommendations are suggested.

Description of Case Study

The University of Coimbra, located in the city of Coimbra in central Portugal, stands as one of Europe's oldest universities and holds the prestigious UNESCO World Heritage Site designation. Founded in 1290, the university boasts a rich legacy of academic excellence and cultural significance. Its architectural wonders, spanning the Renaissance, Baroque, and Gothic periods, reflect the history and culture of the city and of the country.

While the university's buildings are dispersed throughout the urban centre, they primarily cluster in three main areas or campuses, as depicted in Figure 38. Additional buildings owned by the University of Coimbra, like the Palácio de São Marcos, exist at a greater distance and thus fall beyond the scope of this case study, given they surpass the distance limits stipulated by regulations.

Figure 38. Location of the University Campuses in Coimbra city (Adapted from University of Coimbra)

The University's main campus, Polo I, is located in the upper part of the city centre (Figure 39). This campus includes several historic buildings such

as the Joanina Library and the Royal Palace, museums, departments, the Faculties of Law, Arts and Humanities, and the Botanical Garden.

**Figure 39. Main campus of the University of Coimbra – Polo I
(Source: University of Coimbra)**

Polo II is located on the right bank of the Mondego River and houses the Faculty of Science and Technology, which includes all the Engineering departments (Figure 40). Its construction began in 1992, and most departments' inauguration occurred in 2001. Hence, the construction

typology of the buildings is very different from Polo I. Since it was built in a peripheral and uninhabited area of the city, it has a larger area available for expansion and implementation of renewable generation systems.

Figure 40. Mechanical Engineering Department at the second campus of the University of Coimbra – Polo II (Source: University of Coimbra)

The most recent campus, Polo III, hosts the Health Sciences faculties and is located close to the University Hospital (Figure 41), and is still undergoing an expansion

process. Despite being more recent than the others, the buildings' roofs and the available space represent some obstacles to the installation of RES such as photovoltaic panels.

Figure 41. Campus of the University of Coimbra– Polo III (Source: University of Coimbra)

Determined by the aim of being the first carbon-neutral Portuguese university, recently the University of Coimbra has made significant efforts to reduce its energy consumption and carbon footprint through its Strategic Plan (University of Coimbra, 2019), in line with the Long-term Strategy for Carbon Neutrality of the Portuguese Economy (Ministry of Environment and Energy Transition, 2019). To reach this goal, the university has implemented a range of measures, such as energy-efficient lighting, solar water heating, and building retrofits, to reduce its energy consumption and greenhouse gas emissions. Due to these measures, the University of Coimbra has succeeded in reducing its total annual energy consumption by 17% (Figure 42), and its carbon footprint, the equivalent of 1031 tons of CO₂, between 2019 and 2021 (Figure 43). By the end of 2023, the University of Coimbra intends to reduce its carbon footprint by 20-25%

and increase the installed power of renewables by 75-100%, according to the 2019-2023 Strategic Plan of the University of Coimbra¹ (SPUC). Besides the education for sustainability through degree programs and research opportunities in related fields, such as renewable energy, environmental science, and sustainable development, the University of Coimbra has created a sustainability office to promote social and environmental awareness among its students and staff.

Figure 42. University of Coimbra – Total Energy Consumption (GWh) (Source: University of Coimbra)

Figure 43. University of Coimbra - Equivalent Carbon Emissions (Sources: University of Coimbra)

To reinforce the commitment to achieving carbon neutrality, this case study focuses on assessing the potential of implementing a REC in the university's facilities with carbon capture strategies. Firstly, by implementing a REC,

the institution can increase the contribution of renewable energy sources to meet its demand and increase the energy citizenship of its participants, namely the students. Secondly, carbon

capture strategies are critical to balance hard-to-avoid emissions (Directorate-General for Climate Action, 2023), acting as a strong ally for the university to be the first climate-neutral university in Portugal.

REC Regulatory Framework – analysis

Within the European context, the primary directives addressing REC are the Renewable Energy Directive (RED II) and the Internal Electricity Market Directive. Among the member states, the best examples of putting into practice these directives are Denmark, Belgium, Germany, France, Ireland, and Italy (Figure 44). Regarding Portugal, as outlined by Crispim et al. (2023), the country's regulatory framework reflects a commitment to advancing energy transition. This commitment manifests through citizen involvement through both self-consumption and active participation in REC initiatives.

Nonetheless, the European Federation of Citizen Energy Cooperatives (Rescoop.EU) identified four specific points where the transposition of the abovementioned directives can be improved (REScoop.EU, 2022):

- The Portuguese regulatory framework needs to address issues such as the autonomy of REC.
- The Portuguese regulatory framework ignores the fundamental concept of REC, ownership, allowing the creation of REC with RES owned by third parties.
- The Portuguese regulatory framework does not clearly distinguish the differences between CER and collective self-consumption.
- The Portuguese regulatory framework considers the geographical proximity of renewable energy production facilities not only as a criterion for choosing the managing entity but also as a criterion for choosing

the members that may participate in the REC, constituting a limitation to citizens' participation in this type of initiative.

According to Decree-Law No. 15/2022, the main regulatory document for REC in Portugal, the key requirements for the establishment of a REC in Portugal are:

- A REC can be formed by natural or legal persons of a public or private nature through voluntary membership.
- A REC should primarily aim to provide environmental, economic, and social benefits, rather than financial gains, to its members and the surrounding community through the production, consumption, storage, and trade of renewable energy between its members and third parties.
- The participating members need to be located in the proximity of the renewable

energy project, more specifically with a distance of less than 2 km in the case of low voltage connections, less than 4 km with medium voltage connections, less than 10 km with high voltage connections and less than 20 km with very high voltage connections.

- An internal regulation is mandatory to define clearly the operation of the specific REC.
- It is necessary to define a management entity of collective self-consumption to manage the community as well as to represent the REC in the most diverse instances.
- For the licensing of the renewable installations, it is necessary to make a prior communication to the General Directorate for Energy and Geology (DGEG).

**Figure 44. Transposition tracker – REC and CEC definitions
(Source: Rescoop.EU)**

Besides this diploma, the regulatory framework around REC is also composed by Self-Consumption Regulation (ERSE, 2022) from the Energy Services Regulatory Entity (ERSE) as well as the Directive n° 12/2022 (ERSE, 2022). The purpose of the self-consumption regulation is to regulate the commercial relationship between the agents participating in self-consumption allowing greater effectiveness in the implementation of the REC, as

well as to regulate the use of the networks, which tariff calculation is presented in the Tariff Regulation (ERSE, 2020). In the case of Directive n° 12/2022, it presents the general conditions of contracts for the use of networks for self-consumption.

Barriers to the implementation of a REC in the University of Coimbra

As mentioned in the Introduction section, there are several barriers to the implementation

of REC. In this case, the main barriers are related to the characteristics of the University of Coimbra buildings, the regulatory framework and the high initial investment required.

The UNESCO World Heritage classification and the historic building structures are subject to strict preservation rules and regulations. In heritage buildings, besides the common building barriers as the limited roof space for solar panels and limited space nearby for wind turbines, the integration of RES is limited by architectural, conservation and cultural barriers (Tsoumanis et al., 2021).

Regarding the regulatory framework, the proximity parameters established in Decree-law nº 15/2022 for the establishment of a REC is a barrier. The University of Coimbra has their buildings spread around the city and considering that the electricity produced by photovoltaic panels will be injected into the

grid at medium voltage, it limits the area of the REC of the University of Coimbra to a range of 4 km from the point of injection into the grid. Consequently, certain structures, like the Palácio de São Marcos, are ineligible for inclusion in this initiative, despite their favourable conditions for photovoltaic system installation.

In addition to this regulatory obstacle, and despite not being directly related to the regulatory framework, the licensing period for new renewable projects at the DGEG, including REC, stands as a noteworthy concern. While the REPowerEU Plan aimed to truncate the licensing timeline for renewable projects from 6 to 3 months, these timelines have not been adhered to by member states, Portugal included (European Commission, 2022d; Fox et al., 2022; Lusa, 2023).

Finally, another barrier is the high upfront investment needed to implement a RES in such a large institution. The cost of implementing RES can be high, especially in historic buildings

where preservation requirements may increase the cost (Tsoumanis et al., 2021). In addition, the initial investment cost for installing RES can be challenging for universities to justify.

Case Study Solution

Given the significant total energy consumption of the facilities comprising the University of Coimbra, and to generate an amount of energy capable of satisfying a non-negligible portion of this consumption, in addition to allowing energy exchange with other consumers, the photovoltaic systems to be installed must inevitably have a considerable size. Thus, an analysis of the available areas in each university campus was first carried out, both in terms of rooftops and land, using the QGIS[1] software.

Following this analysis, and given the characteristics of the university campuses, it

became apparent that Polo II is the most suitable location for installing these systems due to various factors. Firstly, Polo II exhibits the highest availability of land, which fulfils the projected requirements. Additionally, unlike Polo I, there are no restrictions concerning historic buildings, eliminating potential obstacles associated with preservation regulations. From this analysis, two plots of land located in Polo II were selected to evaluate the potential installation of the photovoltaic systems, as presented in Figure 45.

QGIS is an open-source Geographic Information System (GIS) software that allows users to view, analyse, and edit geospatial data.

Energy Analysis

The renewable energy production of the systems was estimated using Helioscope[1] solar design software, which offers features that help streamline several stages of the process, including design, layout, and performance

analysis. For this and using the technical data of the selected photovoltaic modules, several simulations were performed with different parameters, such as orientations, inclination angles and numbers of panels. Having as restrictions the energy consumption of the University facilities, the available space, the technical characteristics of the photovoltaic modules and other components, and the costs and viability of the systems, these analyses allowed defining the size of

the photovoltaic systems to be installed. The annual production series for the designed photovoltaic plant was extracted from the software and used for the analysis in this study.

After determining the anticipated energy generated by the photovoltaic systems, it is essential to ascertain which portion of this energy will be self-consumed by the institution's facilities and which will be the surplus sold to other consumers, such as industrial ones, as part of this REC.

Figure 45. Possible locations for PV installation
[Provided by: Cleanwatts, SA]

Given that the primary purpose of establishing this Local Energy Community is to contribute to the University of Coimbra's pursuit of carbon neutrality, prime attention has been devoted to the University's diverse buildings. These buildings are spread across three different campuses as well as throughout the city, serving as recipients of the energy produced by the Community, as depicted in Figure 46. In this visual representation, each circle corresponds to the installed power of each building. This group of buildings comprises a total of 80 buildings, 35 of which are supplied at normal low voltage, 28 at special low voltage, and 17 at medium voltage. One building (Palácio de São Marcos) was excluded from this group because it is located at a distance from the other buildings and the production systems greater than the established limit (4 Km), as represented in Figure 46, making its inclusion inviable.

The energy consumption of this group of buildings was obtained in several ways. In the case of facilities supplied at medium voltage or special low voltage, the quarter-hourly data was directly accessed through the platform provided to this type of customer by the distribution operator. This data is made available through measurement equipment installed by the operator. On the other hand, for buildings supplied at normal low voltage, the data were obtained through measurements and load diagrams from previous energy audits and studies. Additionally, typical consumption patterns, and the analysis of energy bills were taken into consideration.

By comparing the production data of the photovoltaic systems with the energy consumption of the University buildings, it was possible to determine the proportion of energy produced that would be self-consumed by the University and the portion that would be integrated into the Community for exchange with other consumers, particularly industrial users. After

determining the percentage of energy self-consumed by the University buildings, it is also possible to calculate the annual reduction of the University's energy acquisition

achieved through the photovoltaic systems. These energy-related data lay the foundation for further analyses, including environmental and financial assessments.

Figure 46. Location of the University buildings
[Provided by: Cleanwatts, SA].

Environmental Analysis

The environmental analysis consists in determining the amount of avoided CO₂ emissions resulting from the implementation of this REC. To determine the amount of CO₂ emissions avoided ($CO_2\ avoid$) it is necessary to multiply the a

mount of energy that was avoided from being purchased from the energy supplier (En_{avoid}), being instead produced through this RES, by the emission factor of the Portuguese electroproduction system (FE):

$$CO_2\ avoid = \sum En_{avoid} \times FE$$

In the Portuguese case, the value of the emission factor for the electroproduction system was 250 tons of CO₂ per GWh in 2021 (DGEG, 2021). Finally, the total reduction of CO₂ emissions resulting from the implementation of this REC is obtained by adding two parts, namely the emissions avoided by the University of Coimbra and the emissions avoided by the industrial consumers that will be part of this Community.

Financial Analysis

To evaluate the financial feasibility of the proposed REC, two key financial indicators were considered based on the methodology proposed by Umar et al. (2021):

- *Net Present Value (NPV)*

NPV is used to evaluate the profitability of a project. It calculates the difference between the present value of cash inflows, which includes revenues from electricity sales and electricity savings,

and the present value of cash outflows, while considering the time value of money. The cash outflows encompass initial investment, maintenance costs, grid access fees, and other costs, such as the REC's management services and replacement of inverters and other components. A positive NPV indicates the investment's financial attractiveness, while a negative NPV suggests the investment may not be economically viable or profitable. The annual income revenue from electricity sales for a given year t can be calculated through expression (21), where x_t is the annual amount of electricity sold and C_1 is the stipulated price per kilowatt-hour:

$$\text{Electricity Sales Revenue} = x_t * C_1 \quad (21)$$

In turn, the annual savings revenue for a given year can be calculated through expression (22), where y_t is the annual amount of electricity not purchased and C_2 the average price per kilowatt-hour of the University's buildings:

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$$\text{Electricity Savings Revenue} = y_t * C_2$$

NPV can thus be calculated through expression (4):

$$NPV = -C + \sum_{t=1}^n \frac{Q_t}{(1+d)^t}$$

where C is the initial investment, d is the discount rate, n is the lifetime of the project – in years, t is the specific year for calculation, and Q is the net cash flow. In turn, the net cash flow can be calculated as follows:

$$Q_t = \text{Total Cash Inflows}_t - \text{Total Cash Outflows}_t$$

For this study, several assumptions will be made: a project lifetime of 25 years (Branker et al., 2011), a discount rate of 5%, an annual degradation of 0.8 % in energy production from the PV systems; and an exemption of payment of grid access fees for the first 7 years (Legislative Order 6453/2020, June 19th).

Adjusted Payback

Adjusted Payback calculates

the time it takes for an investment to recover its initial cost, considering the time value of money. Shorter payback periods indicate quicker cost recovery and reduced risk. It can be calculated by the following equation, where t^* is the number of years before full recovery:

$$\text{Adjusted Payback} = t^* + \frac{C - \sum_{t=1}^{t^*} \frac{Q_t}{(1+d)^t}}{\frac{Q_{t^*+1}}{(1+d)^{t^*+1}}}$$

To find t^* it is necessary to sum the discounted net cash flows (Q) up to the year preceding the year in which the entire investment is recovered.

Carbon capture systems

With the goal of complementing the reduction of CO2 emissions achieved through the implementation of the REC, as well as replacing food products with high environmental footprints, practising efficient resource management, and optimizing water consumption, the University of Coimbra plans to test a succession agroforestry system (SAFS) on

its campus. Moreover, this agroforestry approach will be enhanced through the incorporation of biochar and soil carbon sequestration techniques. This forward-thinking initiative aligns perfectly with the pillars of its sustainability strategy, demonstrating the University of Coimbra's commitment to maintaining its position as one of Europe's most sustainable universities and a prominent institution in Portugal (University of Coimbra, 2019).

Results and Discussion

To determine the installed capacity of the photovoltaic systems to be implemented, various restrictions were taken into consideration. The first constraint was the available land area in Polo II, which was identified through analysis using the QGIS software. The second constraint is related to the selection of photovoltaic modules. In this case, the monocrystalline type from JA Solar, model JAM72D30-550/MB, was chosen. It offers a maximum rated power of 550 Wp and an efficiency of 21.2 %. The third constraint is related to the energy consumption profile of the University buildings.

By utilizing the HelioScope software and incorporating the existing constraints, this study assumes the installation of two photovoltaic systems with an approximate installed power of 3.16 MW and 4.33 MW, resulting in a total installed capacity of 7.49 MW. Table 16 depicts detailed information about these systems, such as the occupied area and the number of modules.

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sustainability strategy, demonstrating the University of Coimbra's commitment to maintaining its position as one of Europe's most sustainable universities and a prominent institution in Portugal (University of Coimbra, 2019).

Table 16. General data of the production units to be installed.

Site	Area (m ²)	Azimuth	Tilt angle	Number of modules	Installed Power (kW)
1	39286	~0°	35°	5740	3157
2	45164	~0°	35°	7868	4327

Based on the results of the final simulation (Figure 47), the systems are anticipated to generate an estimated annual

energy production of 10.8 GWh, which corresponds to a total of 1444 equivalent hours of production at the selected coordinates.

Figure 47. Layout of the PV systems to be installed.

Energy balance:

By interconnecting the estimated production series of the PV plants with the consumption points associated with the University buildings, an energy balance

was derived. This balance reveals the percentage of generated energy consumed by the University facilities, in addition to the surplus that will be allocated to the other consumers that will be part of the REC (Table 17).

Table 17. REC energy balance.

	Energy (GWh)	Percentage (%)
<i>Consumed by UC</i>	6.45	59.7 %
<i>Consumed by other REC members</i>	4.35	40.3 %
<i>UC consumption supplied by REC</i>	-	38.8 %

This energy balance shows that, based on the consumption profile of the buildings, it is predicted that approximately 60 % of the energy produced by the REC, namely 6.45 GWh, will be internally consumed by the University of Coimbra's buildings, making up approximately 38.8 % of its total energy consumption. These values demonstrate that investing in this initiative can significantly promote the adoption of renewable energy

and help reduce the environmental impact resulting from the institution's energy usage, therefore enhancing its overall sustainability. Furthermore, despite the initial high investment, this initiative will yield long-term financial benefits by reducing energy purchases by approximately 39 % of the university's total annual energy consumption. Thus, the project not only contributes to environmental sustainability, but also enhances financial sustainability.

However, the benefits of this project extend beyond the University of Coimbra. The results indicate that around 40 % of the energy generated by the REC, approximately 4.35 GWh, could be consumed by other members that will be part of this Community, namely industrial consumers situated in the vicinity of these projects. By participating in this project, these consumers can also experience reduced energy purchases from typical retailers and CO2 emissions, thereby improving their financial efficiency and promoting the decarbonization of their operations.

RECs typically involve residential consumers as part of their implementation strategy. This approach serves multiple goals, including addressing energy poverty, particularly among low-income families, and enhancing the social impact and viability of the project. Nevertheless, REC also aim to foster citizen engagement in

decarbonization and energy transition. Industrial consumers were prioritized, as one of the main purposes is to reduce the environmental footprint of industrial operations and facilitate the adoption of renewable energy in the industrial sector, contributing to energy resilience, an important pillar of smart manufacturing. The inclusion of university residences and low-income residential consumers located in the neighbourhood could be further considered in the next phase of this project, thus also contributing to the energy poverty issue.

Environmental balance:

Considering the value of the emission factor of the Portuguese electroproduction system of 2021, namely 250 tons of CO2 per GWh, it is possible to verify that this project, through local generation of renewable energy, allows to avoid 2700 tons of annual CO2 emissions. Table 19 illustrates the annual CO2 emissions reduction for both the University of Coimbra

and the participating industrial consumers involved in this initiative.

By adopting this sustainable solution, the University of Coimbra not only contributes to the decarbonization and improved sustainability of the Portuguese industrial sector but also achieves a significant

reduction in its annual CO₂ emissions from its energy consumption. The reduction is estimated at 29 %, bringing the University closer to its goal of achieving carbon neutrality. This demonstrates the university's commitment to addressing environmental challenges while promoting a cleaner and greener future.

Table 19. CO₂ emissions avoided.

	CO ₂ emission avoided (ton)
<i>University of Coimbra</i>	1612
<i>Industrial consumers</i>	1088
<i>Total</i>	2700

Financial balance:

As with other initiatives, the financial component plays a fundamental role, as it can often be one of the main barriers to project initiation and development. Therefore, it is essential to conduct a thorough financial evaluation of this project, bearing in mind that the primary objective is not to generate profits but

rather to decrease the energy dependence of the involved institutions and companies, reduce their CO₂ emissions, and enhance the sustainability of their operations. In this regard, two financial metrics were evaluated: net present value and adjusted payback.

To initiate the analysis, the initial investment was estimated at

6,124,342€ (including VAT), using data from the HelioScope software and budgeting by various companies. Then, the remaining components of the project's cash outflow were determined: grid access fees, maintenance costs, and other costs including REC management services, inverters' replacement, insurance, etc. To determine the grid access costs, the legislation defining the values approved by the regulator (ERSE) was consulted, and an average value of 0.025€/kWh

was defined. Furthermore, it was considered that, as has been seen in this type of project, there is an exemption of payment of grid access fees for the first 7 years (Legislative Order 6453/2020, June 19th). In turn, to determine the remaining costs (maintenance costs, inverters' replacement, management services, etc.) several companies were consulted. Figure 48 illustrates the variation of the cash outflow's components over the project's lifetime, apart from the initial investment costs.

Figure 48. Variations of the cash outflow's components over the project's lifetime (except initial investment).

The subsequent focus was on determining the two components of the cash inflow: estimated electricity savings and estimated electricity sales. The estimated electricity savings stem from the portion of the electricity produced that will be consumed by the University's facilities, thereby avoiding its purchase from the energy supplier. For this calculation, and adopting a conservative stance, the weighted average price per kilowatt-hour (kWh) based on

the University buildings' contracts was considered (0.11€). Conversely, the electricity sales are derived from the electricity that will be sold to the industrial consumers, considering an average sale price of 0.06 €/kWh, which is a highly competitive tariff in this segment. Figure 49 illustrates the variations in both cash inflow components over the project's lifetime, accounting for an annual degradation rate of 0.8 % of the electricity production.

Figure 49. Variations of the two parts of the cash inflow over the project's lifetime.

Based on the previously determined values and considering a discount rate of 5 % and a project lifetime of 25 years as assumptions, the project's financial analysis reveals a positive NPV of 3,576,063 € and an adjusted payback of about 9.8 years. These values demonstrate that the project is financially attractive in the time considered and that the investment can be recovered in an acceptable period, while achieving the main objectives, namely reducing CO₂ emissions and energy dependence of the institutions and companies involved and increasing the sustainability of their operations. To further improve the payback period, complementary strategies like selling electricity to residential consumers at higher tariffs or implementing dynamic tariffs based on periods could be explored. Figure 50 shows the evolution of the project's NPV and other financial indicators over time.

Contribution to Smart Manufacturing:

The implementation of this REC, focused on photovoltaic production, and the consequent inclusion of industrial consumers, plays a key role in advancing smart manufacturing practices. By establishing a local and sustainable energy supply, industries gain access to an environmentally friendly energy supply, resulting in higher energy resilience and stability and reducing concerns over energy availability and energy cost fluctuations. Furthermore, it also leads to reduced overall operating and production costs over time through the resulting energy cost savings, thereby making manufacturing industries more economically viable by enhancing their competitiveness and productivity in the global market. In addition, the resulting cost savings also enable greater capacity to invest in technologies and further enhance the development of smart manufacturing.

Figure 50. Evolution of NPV, discounted net cash flow, and discounted cumulative cash flow over time.

From an environmental point of view, given the current environmental problems and consumption of natural resources, this project makes an important contribution to enhancing the environmental sustainability of the involved industrial consumers. By reducing dependence on fossil fuels and fostering the adoption of cleaner energy alternatives, this project helps industrial consumers to significantly lower their carbon emissions and move closer to the overall goal of decarbonizing their

production processes, another of the main objectives of smart manufacturing.

Agroforestry for Carbon Capture

Agroforestry, as a nature-based solution for carbon capture, proves to be highly cost-effective and a promising approach to combat climate change (Erbach & Victoria, 2021). This approach generates significant returns on investment and economic benefits, driven by enhanced crop productivity

(Kim et al., 2016; Zomer et al., 2016). Furthermore, once established, this system is relatively self-sustaining, requiring minimal inputs and management in contrast to other carbon removal technologies. Farmers can benefit from both marketable timber and non-timber forest products, in addition to crops or livestock raised within the system.

Given the increasing recognition of agroforestry, with special emphasis on succession agroforestry systems (SAFS), the University of Coimbra intends to apply this type of system on its campus. SAFS mimic the natural succession processes of ecosystems and integrate them into agricultural practices (Dufty et al., 2000; Goetsch, 1992; Montagnini & Ashton, 1999; PENEIREIRO, 1999; B. Schulz et al., 1994; J. Schulz, 2011; Vaz, 2000; Vieira et al., 2009). In SAFS, each plant species is provided with optimal conditions for growth, occupying their natural positions in both space (stratification) and time

(succession). To accomplish these objectives, SAFS focuses on creating species combinations that exhibit functional behaviours similar to important natural successional stages (Goetsch, 1992; PENEIREIRO, 1999; J. Schulz, 2011; Vaz, 2000; Vieira et al., 2009).

With the aforementioned in mind, the University of Coimbra will adopt an alley-cropping design for its SAFS, inspired by successful practices observed in many Portuguese agroforestry farms (Leitão, 2022). The SAFS design involves planting trees and/or shrubs to establish alleys where agricultural or horticultural crops can thrive. Therefore, its stratification will entail spaced rows of fruit orchards, like citrus, olives or others, intermixed with forestry trees, such as poplar or eucalyptus, used for multipurpose functions and occupying the upper layer of the SAFS. These trees will provide physical protection to crops and contribute to biomass production (pruning), possibly

for biochar. Vegetables like tomatoes, peppers, lettuce, green beans, and cabbage, among others, will grow in two or three beds within the alleys, filling the lowest strata and the early phases of succession, mimicking forest succession processes and supporting valuable tree growth, particularly fruit trees. Placing a specific tree species closely together maximizes photosynthesis.

The University of Coimbra's planned SAFS aims to sequester CO₂ emissions from campus activities through photosynthesis. Simultaneously, these systems will yield diverse fruits and vegetables, suitable for the campus canteen, following the example set by Paladin at the Mendes Gonçalves S.A. farm, or potential sale, using a business model like what is observed at Quinta da Manguela or Planta Floresta farms (Leitão, 2022). Beyond these practical applications, the SAFS will also serve as an educational and research

field, mimicking the role played by farms such as Quinta do Monte or Herdade do Freixo do Meio (Leitão, 2022).

Finally, to complement CO₂ sequestration and enrich soil quality, water retention capacity, and nutrient availability, biochar will be incorporated into the soil as part of the cultivation preparation process. This can be achieved through soil carbon sequestration techniques like low or no-tillage, which mitigate carbon release from the land to the atmosphere (Lal, 2004; Li & Pang, 2010).

Conclusion and Recommendations

This case study aims to demonstrate how the commitment to energy transition, through the installation of photovoltaic plants and the creation of a REC, will enhance clean energy production and reduce not only the carbon footprint of the University of Coimbra,

but also increase energy autonomy and reduce the institution's energy costs. According to the results, implementing this REC would provide about 38.8 % of the University's annual electricity consumption, a total of 6.45 GWh. This local generation of renewable energy would allow a substantial annual reduction in energy costs and CO₂ emissions, contributing significantly to the financial and environmental sustainability of the institution, and bringing the University of Coimbra closer to the established carbon neutrality objective.

The case study also highlights that the project's benefits extend beyond the University, demonstrating its significance in driving energy transition and smart manufacturing. According to the results, approximately 40% of the energy generated by the REC, equivalent to around 4.35 GWh, could be utilized by industrial consumers in the project's vicinity. By participating in the REC, industrial consumers can benefit from reduced energy purchases and CO₂

emissions, leading to improved financial efficiency and enhanced energy resilience, while promoting the decarbonization and environmental sustainability of their industrial activities. The resulting energy cost savings further contribute to reduced operating and production costs, boosting the competitiveness of manufacturing industries in the global market. Moreover, these savings increase the capacity to invest in technologies and further enhance the development of smart manufacturing.

The project's financial analysis indicates a net present value of 3,576,063 € and an adjusted payback of approximately 9.8 years. These results affirm the project's financial attractiveness within the considered timeframe, ensuring a reasonable period for the investment to be recovered. Moreover, the project successfully aligns with its main objectives, which encompass reducing CO₂

emissions and energy dependence of the institutions and companies involved, as well as increasing the sustainability of their operations. Overall, the financial viability, coupled with environmental advantages, underscores the project's potential success. Moreover, in the later stages of the project, complementary strategies like selling electricity to residential consumers at higher tariffs or implementing dynamic tariffs based on periods could be explored to further improve the payback period, as well as include low-income residential consumers to tackle energy poverty.

Simultaneously, the results allow to increase the general population's knowledge regarding this subject, serving as potential awareness material and as an example to mobilize citizens, companies, and institutions to follow this example and enhance the implementation of RECs that are not limited to the residential and service sectors, but also integrate the industrial sector.

The University of Coimbra's SAFS aligns seamlessly with its sustainability strategy, acting as a pivotal reinforcement to the University's REC in significantly curtailing CO₂ emissions arising from campus activities. The integration of biochar and soil carbon sequestration techniques will amplify the SAFS' effectiveness. In comparison to other carbon dioxide removal options, the University of Coimbra's SAFS exhibits remarkable cost-effectiveness. Notably, considering the revenues generated from product sales, the costs of carbon sequestration might even be negative.

In summary, this case study demonstrates that collaboration and symbiosis between higher education institutions, currently committed to the energy transition and decarbonization of society, and industrial companies, typically characterized by their intensive consumption of

energy and resources, in the development of renewable energy production projects and the creation of REC can be an interesting solution to promote energy transition and smart manufacturing. The results illustrate that, despite the initial costs, this type of project is financially viable and brings additional benefits beyond financial ones, including increased energy resilience, enhanced competitiveness, and reduced CO₂ emissions from operations and activities. In addition, the environmental benefits for education institutions and companies can be further enhanced through complementary implementation of carbon capture solutions. As such, this type of initiative should be promoted and replicated by other institutions and companies.

References

- Branker, K., Pathak, M. J. M., & Pearce, J. M. (2011). A review of solar photovoltaic levelized cost of electricity. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 15(9), 4470–4482.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2011.07.104>
- Brummer, V. (2018). Community energy – benefits and barriers: A comparative literature review of Community Energy in the UK, Germany and the USA, the benefits it provides for society and the barriers it faces. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 94, 187–196.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2018.06.013>
- Cabeza, L. F., de Gracia, A., & Pisello, A. L. (2018). Integration of renewable technologies in historical and heritage buildings: A review. *Energy and Buildings*, 177, 96–111. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2018.07.058>
- Creutzig, F., Breyer, C., Hilaire, J., Minx, J., Peters, G. P., & Socolow, R. (2019). The mutual dependence of negative emission technologies and energy systems. *Energy & Environmental Science*, 12(6), 1805–1817.
<https://doi.org/10.1039/C8EE03682A>
- Crispim, J. M., Mendes, J. G., Antunes, A. R., Azevedo, I., Carreiro, A., Ferreira, L., Villar, J., & Mello, J. (2023). Comunidades de Energia Renovável. In *Comunidades de Energia Renovável*.
<https://doi.org/10.21814/uminho.ed.109>
- Dai, R., Hu, M., Yang, D., & Chen, Y. (2015). A collaborative operation decision model for distributed building clusters. *Energy*, 84, 759–773.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2015.03.042>
- DGEG. (2021). Indicadores Energéticos.
<https://www.dgeg.gov.pt/pt/estatistica/energia/indicadores-energeticos/>

- Directorate-General for Climate Action. (2023). Carbon removals: a strong ally to achieve climate neutrality in the EU. https://climate.ec.europa.eu/news-your-voice/news/carbon-removals-strong-ally-achieve-climate-neutrality-eu-2023-02-17_en
- Dufty, A. C., Senanayake, F. R., Jack, J., & Melvarni, K. (2000). Analogue Forestry - A Total Ecosystem Management Approach that Maximises Biodiversity within Plantation Agriculture. *The Planter*, 671–696.
- Erbach, G., & Victoria, A. G. (2021). Carbon Dioxide removal: Nature-based and technological solutions. European Parliament Climate Action Research and Tracking Service, February.
- ERSE. (2020). Regulamento Tarifário do setor elétrico. https://www.erse.pt/media/bhnpuida/articulado-rt-se_consolidado.pdf
- ERSE. (2022). Directive no 12/2022. *Diário Da República* n.o 97/2022, Série II de 2022-05-19, 152–158. https://www.erse.pt/media/zthbik1e/regulamento-n-o-373_2021.pdf
- European Commission. (2016). The Road from Paris: assessing the implications of the Paris Agreement and accompanying the proposal for a Council decision on the signing, on behalf of the European Union, of the Paris agreement adopted under the United Nations Framework Convention on Cl. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52016DC0110>
- European Commission. (2019). Clean energy for all Europeans. 14(2), 3. <https://doi.org/10.2833/9937>
- European Commission. (2020). A European Green Deal. https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal_en

- European Commission. (2022a). Energy and the Green Deal. https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal/energy-and-green-deal_en
- European Commission. (2022b). In focus: Energy communities to transform the EU's energy system. https://energy.ec.europa.eu/news/focus-energy-communities-transform-eus-energy-system-2022-12-13_en
- European Commission. (2022c). Proposal for a Directive of the European Parliament and of the Council amending Directive (EU) 2018/2001 on the promotion of the use of energy from renewable sources, Directive 2010/31/EU on the energy performance of buildings and Directive 2012/27/EU on. <https://doi.org/10.2833/239077>
- Fox, H., Czyżak, P., & Brown, S. (2022). Ready, Set, Go: Europe's Race for Wind and Solar. <https://ember-climate.org/insights/research/europes-race-for-wind-and-solar/>
- Giordano, A., Mastroianni, C., Menniti, D., Pinnarelli, A., & Sorrentino, N. (2019). An Energy Community Implementation: The Unical Energy Cloud. *Electronics*, 8(12), 1517. <https://doi.org/10.3390/electronics8121517>
- Goetsch, E. (1992). NATURAL SUCCESSION OF SPECIES IN AGROFORESTRY AND IN SOIL RECOVERY. https://www.agrofloresta.net/static/artigos/agroforestry_1992_gotsch.pdf
- Kim, D.-G., Kirschbaum, M. U. F., & Beedy, T. L. (2016). Carbon sequestration and net emissions of CH₄ and N₂O under agroforestry: Synthesizing available data and suggestions for future studies. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, 226, 65–78. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2016.04.011>

- Koch, A., & Girard, S. (2011). Urban neighbourhoods – an intermediate scale for the assessment of energy performance of buildings. ECEEE 2011 Summer Study Energy Efficiency First: The Foundation of a Low-Carbon Society, 1377–1385.
- Kubli, M., & Puranik, S. (2023). A typology of business models for energy communities: Current and emerging design options. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 176(December 2022), 113165. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2023.113165>
- Lal, R. (2004). Soil Carbon Sequestration Impacts on Global Climate Change and Food Security. *Science*, 304(5677), 1623–1627. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1097396>
- Li, G.-L., & Pang, X.-M. (2010). Effect of land-use conversion on C and N distribution in aggregate fractions of soils in the southern Loess Plateau, China. *Land Use Policy*, 27(3), 706–712. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2009.09.011>
- Lusa. (2023). Cleanwatts tem 57 comunidades de energia há mais de um ano à espera de licença. <https://eco.sapo.pt/2023/01/31/cleanwatts-tem-57-comunidades-de-energia-ha-mais-de-um-ano-a-espera-de-licenca/>
- Marrone, P., Fiume, F., Laudani, A., Montella, I., Palermo, M., & Fulginei, F. R. (2023). Distributed Energy Systems: Constraints and Opportunities in Urban Environments. *Energies*, 16(6), 2718. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en16062718>
- Ministry of Environment and Energy Transition. (2019). ROTEIRO PARA A NEUTRALIDADE CARBÓNICA 2050. https://unfccc.int/sites/default/files/resource/RNC2050_PT-22-09-2019.pdf

- Montagnini, F., & Ashton, M. S. (1999). *The Silvicultural Basis For Agroforestry Systems*. CRC Press. <https://www.routledge.com/The-Silvicultural-Basis-For-Agroforestry-Systems/Montagnini-Ashton/p/book/9780849322068>
- PENEIREIRO, F. M. (1999). Peneireiro, F. M. (1999). *Sistemas agroflorestais dirigidos pela sucessão natural: um estudo de caso*. Universidade de São Paulo: Sao Paulo, Brazil. [University of São Paulo]. <http://www.lerf.esalq.usp.br/divulgacao/produzidos/dissertacoes/peneireiro1999.pdf>
- REScoop.EU. (2022). *Transposition tracker - Definitions*. <https://www.rescoop.eu/transposition-tracker>
- Schulz, B., Becker, B., & Götsch, E. (1994). Indigenous knowledge in a “modern” sustainable agroforestry system – a case study from eastern Brazil. *Agroforestry Systems*, 59–69. https://www.naturefund.de/fileadmin/pdf/Studien/DAF/Schulz_Becker_Goetsch_1994_SAFS.pdf
- Schulz, J. (2011). *Imitating Natural Ecosystems through Successional Agroforestry for the Regeneration of Degraded Lands - A Case Study of Smallholder Agriculture in Northeastern Brazil*. In *Agroforestry as a tool for landscape restoration: challenges and opportunities for success*. (pp. 3–17). Nova Science Publishers, New York. <https://restoration.elti.yale.edu/resource/imitating-natural-ecosystems-through-successional-agroforestry-regeneration-degraded-lands>
- Tsoumanis, G., Formiga, J., Bilo, N., Tsarchopoulos, P., Ioannidis, D., & Tzovaras, D. (2021). The smart evolution of historical cities: Integrated innovative solutions supporting the energy transition while respecting cultural heritage. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 13(16). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13169358>

- Umar, N. H., Bora, B., Banerjee, C., Gupta, P., & Anjum, N. (2021). Performance and economic viability of the PV system in different climatic zones of Nigeria. *Sustainable Energy Technologies and Assessments*, 43(November 2020), 100987. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seta.2020.100987>
- University, A. (2020). Carbon Removal Fact Sheets & Resources. <https://www.american.edu/sis/centers/carbon-removal/fact-sheets.cfm>
- University of Coimbra. (2019). 2019-2023 Strategic Plan of the University of Coimbra. https://www.uc.pt/en/planning/2019_2023_StrategicPlanUC.pdf
- Vaz, P. (2000). Regenerative analog agroforestry in Brazil. *ILEIA NEWSLETTER*. <https://edepot.wur.nl/80475>
- Vieira, D. L. M., Holl, K. D., & Peneireiro, F. M. (2009). Agro-Successional Restoration as a Strategy to Facilitate Tropical Forest Recovery. *Restoration Ecology*, 17(4), 451–459. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1526-100X.2009.00570.x>
- Wennersten, R., Sun, Q., & Li, H. (2015). The future potential for Carbon Capture and Storage in climate change mitigation – an overview from perspectives of technology, economy and risk. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 103, 724–736. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2014.09.023>
- Zomer, R. J., Neufeldt, H., Xu, J., Ahrends, A., Bossio, D., Trabucco, A., van Noordwijk, M., & Wang, M. (2016). Global Tree Cover and Biomass Carbon on Agricultural Land: The contribution of agroforestry to global and national carbon budgets. *Scientific Reports*, 6(1), 29987. <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep29987>

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